

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): Exploring opportunities for UK Digital Research Infrastructure workshop summary

UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Congress 2025

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹ aims to provide researchers and innovators in Europe with an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research and innovation.

EOSC is now in the next stage of its evolution, with the development of the first national and thematic nodes. There are increasing opportunities for the UK to get involved, both at national and disciplinary levels.

This 90-minute workshop was co-organised by the Digital Curation Centre², UKRI³, and Jisc⁴ and aimed to provide participants of the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Congress 2025⁵ with an opportunity to:

- find out about EOSC's development and opportunities to get involved. Participants heard from speakers and panellists involved in EOSC's governance and the development of national and thematic nodes.
- share views and priorities for UK digital research infrastructure and how these could be supported through developing further links with EOSC. Participants' views will help inform ongoing discussions about UK national involvement in EOSC.

The workshop was chaired by **Helen Clare, Senior e-Infrastructure Strategy Manager, Jisc** and consisted of short talks followed by group discussion. Please see Annex 2 for the detailed agenda.

Our first speaker was **Rachel Bruce, Head of Open Research, UKRI & EOSC Steering Board UK Representative** who provided an **introduction to EOSC** and the UK's involvement to date. Rachel explained that EOSC aims to provide seamless access to tools and resources to enable sharing and reuse of data that are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable). A key aim is to ensure that EOSC becomes a sustainable set of federated, trusted services maintained by member states and which drives better research and realises efficiencies. EOSC has been in its development phase for the past decade mainly through European Commission funded projects - many of which the UK has been involved in and in some cases led. Rachel explained that over the past 18 months, EOSC

¹https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

² <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/>

³ <https://www.ukri.org/>

⁴ <https://jisc.ac.uk/>

⁵ <https://www.ukri.org/events/digital-research-infrastructure-dri-congress-2025/>

has shifted into its implementation phase and noted the launch of EOSC EU Node which took place on 22 October 2024^{6 7} as a key milestone.

Next, **Juan Bicarregui, Director PSDI, Scientific Computing, UKRI-STFC & EOSC Association UK Representative** provided an overview of **EOSC governance**. EOSC is governed by a tripartite collaboration between the European Union (represented by the European Commission), the EOSC Association, and Member States and Associated Countries via the EOSC Steering Board⁸. The EOSC Association runs an annual symposium⁹ to highlight key achievements and to promote collaboration on the updating of the the Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda and its Multi-Annual Roadmap¹⁰. EOSC's Federation Handbook¹¹ has been created to serve as a practical guide for organisations that want to make their resources available within and across the EOSC Federation. The EOSC Association currently has 256 members and observers¹² most of which are Research Performing Organisations. Juan noted that UK membership¹³ is currently quite small with only UKRI and Jisc as members and the UK Atomic Energy Authority and the Open University as observers. He acknowledged that BREXIT slowed UK momentum with regard to EOSC engagement and strongly encouraged participants to get more actively involved. Juan explained that there are a number of EOSC Association task forces¹⁴ and opportunity areas¹⁵ which are the main mechanisms to support collaboration and co-creation with the wider research community. Many UK researchers are currently involved in one or more of these groups. An open call for the first wave of candidate nodes at either the geographic level (services for a specific country or region) or at the the thematic level (services for a specific domain) launched in April 2025¹⁶. Thirteen candidate nodes were successful in their application¹⁷. A second call for candidate nodes is currently open and will close in February 2026¹⁸.

Rachel wrapped up the introductory session with a reminder that the UK has been an active contributor during the early development of EOSC through projects such as EOSCpilot which ran from 2018-2021¹⁹. Despite the lack of momentum over the past few years, there are new opportunities for the UK to re-engage. She emphasised that this workshop was meant to provide a chance for the UK DRI community to consider if and how to engage - whether that is through the establishment of a national node, UK DRIs participation in thematic nodes, or in some other way. The workshop was seen as a starting point for these discussions.

⁶<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/news/european-commission-announces-eosc-eu-nodes-transition-full-production>

⁷ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-symposium-2025/>

¹⁰ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/sria-mar/>

¹¹ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-handbook/>

¹² <https://eosc.eu/members/>

¹³ https://eosc.eu/members/?_country=7072

¹⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/>

¹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

¹⁶ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/HORIZON_HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01-EOSC-01

¹⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/welcoming-eosc-federation-major-milestone-open-science-2025-11-05_en

¹⁸ <https://eosc.eu/news/open-calls-to-grow-the-eosc-federation/>

¹⁹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/eosc>

The workshop then provided two case studies to illustrate the practicalities in setting up national and thematic nodes. We first heard from **Jessica Parland-von Essen, Development Manager, CSC and Programme Manager for the EOSC Finland Node**. CSC leads the **Finnish Node** and is a not for profit company providing centralised infrastructure for high performance computing and research data management (RDM). Jessica noted that a key aim for CSC is to bridge silos to enhance research which is aligned to the overarching EOSC ethos. Jessica explained that Finland has a fairly centralised structure and a long history in supporting RDM. Such alignment between CSC's core mission and EOSC aims is important as Jessica also noted that becoming a EOSC node does not come with any additional funding. A key challenge that they face is convincing Finnish service providers to share their services for free with users from other countries. However, while the lack of funding brings challenges, Jessica also stated that it can be quite freeing in other ways. For instance, Finland has a national reference architecture for RDM which has been useful for identifying areas where key concepts align with EOSC and allows CSC to decide on priority areas itself rather than having to work to a set of priorities set out by a funder.

For CSC, the main priority is to focus on enabling interoperability and in many ways EOSC is helping them to achieve this. With regard to the timeframe for delivery, CSC opted for a seven month duration for the work to be carried out. Jessica cautioned potential node applicants to be realistic and mindful of the wording they use in their applications as potential activities can become viewed as planned activities along with expectations for related milestones and deliverables. Jessica explained that national nodes have quite a bit of flexibility in terms of governance. In Finland, the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Interest Group's Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model²⁰ has been used as a framework which has proved useful. Indeed, Jessica notes that involvement in a number of RDA working groups has informed the development of Finnish open science and RDM services. A key component of the Finnish node is the RDM Competence Centre²¹ which provides access to tools but also, crucially, to training, guidance and advice to build skills for research data management and open science. Additional services in the Finnish node include dataset-as-a-service²² and the Fairdata repository²³. There is also ongoing work to collaborate with HPC so that active data can be shared as well as data submitted to repositories. While the node's services²⁴ are browsable to all, they are accessible to Finnish researchers only at the moment and are not yet federated to the EOSC EU node.

We then heard from **Jonthan Tedds, ELIXIR Programme Manager for Scientific Computing & EOSC Coordinator, ELIXIR Hub, Cambridge UK** about establishing a **thematic node for the Life Sciences**. ELIXIR²⁵ is an established pan-European Research

²⁰ Woodford, C., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Payne, K., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Åkerström, W. N., Macneil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., Wood-Charlson, E., & RDA GORC International Model WG. (2023). The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00099>

²¹ <https://csc.fi/en/our-expertise/research-data-management/>

²² <https://research.csc.fi/eosc-the-finnish-candidate-node/dataset-as-a-service/>

²³ <https://research.csc.fi/eosc-services/fairdata-services-2/>

²⁴ <https://research.csc.fi/eosc-the-finnish-candidate-node/>

²⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org>

Infrastructure with permanent members from 22 countries and 240 research institutes. The UK has been a member of ELIXIR since 2013 and the UK node offers 30 services from 28 participating institutes²⁶. ELIXIR-UK is a crucial national node and is co-led by the University of Manchester and the Earlham Institute. ELIXIR's UK node funding comes mainly from national roadmap funding, competitive research grants, EU Structural Funds or Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), trusts and foundations as well as through industry collaboration. Member State contributions are used to coordinate ELIXIR's five year programme of work across the nodes however these funds are not generally used to support new development work. In the past decade, ELIXIR has been actively involved in a number of European Commission funded projects to develop and implement EOSC. For instance, ELIXIR is currently working via the EOSC Entrust²⁷ project to establish a blueprint for trusted research environments (TREs). In 2019, federation with EOSC was defined as a strategic priority for ELIXIR and in 2022 a dedicated EOSC Strategy for ELIXIR was published²⁸.

ELIXIR is one of four large pan-European research infrastructures that has joined up to develop the thematic node Life Sciences Connect²⁹ which started in 2025 and aims to be fully integrated with the EOSC EU Node by 2028. The main motivation for the group's application to establish a thematic node for the life sciences was to be active in shaping EOSC services rather than taking a passive role as an end user only. Jonathan emphasised that as there is no additional funding to support federation, so it is crucial that you prioritise areas that will be of benefit to your infrastructure and user community. In this regard, ELIXIR has volunteered to take a lead on the EOSC Node Partnership MoU. ELIXIR also sees real value arising from any efforts they take to increase the interoperability of their infrastructure beyond the use case of EOSC. In the longer term, it is envisaged that one of the four partners involved in the thematic node will need to take on the role of the legal entity but, for now, the collaboration is governed by a short term MoU between the four partners which has proven sufficient and effective. As ELIXIR's services are free at the point of use, there is less of a concern about who will be able to access services free of charge.

The Life Sciences Connect collaboration is enabling the four partners to cooperate on establishing federated services for working with sensitive data which is a key challenge for researchers in the life sciences. The collaboration has also highlighted the need for advanced authentication tools as MyAccessID³⁰ alone will not be sufficient. There is currently significant effort going into the development of multi-node use cases to demonstrate the potential value of EOSC to researchers. The wide uptake of EOSC services by the research community and demonstrable recognition of their value for improving research will be critical for leveraging ongoing investment and securing longer-term sustainability. Jonathan concluded by encouraging workshop participants to engage with EOSC to ensure that their voices are heard in the ongoing development and implementation activities.

Following the introductory talks the workshop moved on to an **open discussion** chaired by **Carole Goble, Professor of Computer Science, University of Manchester; Joint Head of Node ELIXIR-UK**. Carole reiterated the point that if we want to influence the development

²⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes/uk>

²⁷ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

²⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/7120997>

²⁹ <https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-life-sciences-connect/>

³⁰ <https://wiki.geant.org/spaces/MyAccessID/overview>

of EOSC, then we need to be actively involved (in the room). Carole began by asking the workshop participants how many of them have been involved in an EOSC related project or initiative. The response from the room showed that only a few have had any previous engagement with EOSC directly and that these were mainly the workshop coordinators and speakers.

Participants asked whether a potential EOSC UK Node would be **something new or leverage existing infrastructures**. It was confirmed that any potential UK Node would build on existing research infrastructures rather than creating something from scratch and participants were reminded that there is no new funding attached to setting up a national or thematic node. The work being done through the DRI programme³¹ and the NetworkPlus initiatives were shared as examples that could be built on. Some participants felt that we need to push for the DRI Programme to adopt a more federated approach between the projects as they are currently quite siloed. Aligning with EOSC could be a useful lever for progressing interoperability across distributed projects and infrastructures. One of the participants referred to ongoing work and cautioned that we should avoid duplicating any effort. For instance, ISAMBARD³² is working to address common issues such as Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) and this work should not be duplicated but rather built on.

Several service providers in the UK are already contributing to thematic infrastructure nodes (such as ELIXIR in the Life Science Connect candidate EOSC node) and it isn't clear yet how such contributions might be reflected in any national level EOSC activity. A starting point could be to develop a **shared understanding of the number and range of UK initiatives that are already involved in delivering federated services - especially those involved in other EOSC nodes**. Participants agreed that such a mapping would be very useful and would also help us to identify gaps in our service provision and potential ways to fill these. Germany's Jupyter4NFDI³³ centralised Jupyter Notebook service was cited as an example of a shared solution to fill a current gap. Participants felt that UKRI would have a key role to play in coordinating such a mapping exercise.

One of the participants asked how end users can search across the EOSC nodes to find suitable services. Speakers explained that an EOSC level **service catalogue** doesn't exist yet but that there is ongoing work to develop one as the EOSC Federation matures. In Finland, the creation of a national service catalogue is considered a critical first step that needs to be undertaken and will also help to provide a picture of the national landscape. Many participants agreed that service catalogues need to be developed and some noted that they must also be curated. Others noted that we must bear in mind that service catalogues are most likely going to be accessed by machines rather than by researchers directly. Participants agreed that service catalogues must have good quality and machine actionable metadata. It was noted that there is a risk that national level service catalogues remain only registries until they are actually federated with other EOSC nodes and accessible.

³¹<https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/digital-research-infrastructure-programme/>

³² <https://www.bristol.ac.uk/news/2025/july/isambard-launch.html>

³³ <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/jupyter4nfdi>

One of the participants suggested that EOSC could add extra complexity for smaller RPOs and suggested that we need to ensure that the longer tail are able to engage with EOSC on a level playing field (i.e., not just the Russell Group). All agreed that **equitable access is essential** and that we should be capturing such pain points and working to simplify access. The Jisc banding model³⁴ was mentioned as a possible approach that could be considered.

Participants felt that there is still work to be done to clarify the potential **value and benefits from federating with EOSC**. Participants referred to the theory of change method which explains how given intervention(s) will lead to a desired change. We need to understand what change we want/need and consider if EOSC is the right intervention to realise this change. Participants suggested that we need **clear use cases** as well as cost benefits analyses, and ways to track impact to help with decision making. Participants mentioned that some already exist but that these could be made more visible. Participants felt that use cases need to be based on real life and not just aspirational if they are to be credible and compelling. Participants also felt that use cases should be cross-theme and cross-national which is not trivial and would require some investment of time and resource to carry out.

Participants noted that EOSC is still a work in progress and that the EOSC Federation Handbook can serve as a guide for interested parties. However, participants agreed that we will also need people to oversee all of this which is often the most difficult aspect to get right. For example, who would be accountable if an EOSC service goes down? The handbook does not currently make these kinds of roles and responsibilities clear. The handbook could be refocused to provide a more **service centric viewpoint**.

EOSC Association membership is currently 10,000 euros per year. As noted earlier, the UK has two members and two observers. Given the current financial hardship facing most RPOs in the UK, it was noted that this could be a hard sell to senior management. Participants agreed that we need access to a briefing document that clearly outlines membership costs against a **range of tangible benefits that can be used to help make the case**.

As the discussion wrapped up, participants were encouraged to **get involved**. The open call for the second wave of candidate nodes which closes in February 2026 was considered to be an opportunity for the UK however participants were reminded that membership is just one way to engage. For instance, in Finland many members of CSC staff have been involved in EOSC sub-groups, task forces and opportunity areas prior to their work on the Finish Node being undertaken. Such engagement requires an investment of time and effort but working with peers to advance common challenges is, in most cases, time well spent.

The workshop provided an opportunity for initial discussions around the potential engagement between the UK's Digital Research Infrastructures and the European Open Science Cloud. However, it is clear that many questions remain. Participants agreed that **additional opportunities to share information would be beneficial**. Regardless of whether the UK federates with EOSC, there is still a need to advance federation between the UK DRIs. The workshop coordinators agreed to explore possibilities for providing such

³⁴ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/membership/higher-education-subscription>

opportunities for knowledge exchange and, in the meantime, encouraged participants to make use of the UK EOSC mailing list³⁵ to enable ongoing community discussion.

The workshop coordinators would like to extend their gratitude to the speakers, workshop and discussion chairs, and to the participants for their active contributions to this session.

³⁵ <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=EOSC>

Annex 1: Workshop Abstract

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): exploring opportunities for the UK's digital research infrastructure

UKRI DRI Congress, Interconnected DRI Workshop

22 October 2025

13:15-14:45

Met 15, The Met Hotel, Leeds

Organisers

This workshop was co-organised by the Digital Curation Centre, Jisc and UKRI. Enquiries about this session should be sent to paul.richards@ukri.org.

Abstract

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EOSC is now in the next stage of its evolution, with the development of the first national and thematic nodes. There are increasing opportunities for the UK to get involved, both at national and disciplinary levels.

This workshop aimed to provide participants with the opportunity to:

- find out about EOSC's development and opportunities to get involved. Participants heard from speakers and panellists involved in EOSC's governance and the development of national and thematic nodes.
- share views and priorities for UK DRI and how these could be supported through developing further links with EOSC. Participants' views will help inform ongoing discussions about UK national involvement in EOSC.

Annex 2: Agenda

Chaired by Helen Clare, Senior e-infrastructure strategy manager, Jisc

Time	Topic	Speaker(s)
13:15	Introducing EOSC & context setting	Rachel Bruce , Head of Open Research, UKRI & EOSC Steering Board UK Representative Juan Bicarregui , Director PSDI, Scientific Computing, UKRI-STFC & EOSC Association UK Representative
13:35	Experiences setting up the EOSC National Node for Finland	Jessica Parland-von Essen , Development Manager, CSC
13:50	Experiences setting up the EOSC Life Science Research Thematic Node	Jonathan Tedds , ELIXIR Programme Manager for Scientific Computing & EOSC Coordinator, ELIXIR Hub, Cambridge UK
14:05	Open discussion - risks, opportunities and potential benefits for UK DRIs Outcomes of FAIR-IMPACT UK Roadshow for reference	Carole Goble , Professor of Computer Science, University of Manchester; Joint Head of Node ELIXIR-UK
14:40	Next steps and wrap-up	Helen Clare

Annex 3: Background information

About EOSC:

- [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\) - Research and innovation](#)
- [Building the EOSC Federation - EOSC Association](#)

About EOSC EU Node and Finland Candidate Node

- [The European Commission Announces the EOSC EU Node Moving to Full Production](#)
- [Welcome to the EOSC Finland Candidate Node - Services for Research](#)

EOSC Association - UK national information page

- [United Kingdom - EOSC Association](#)

To highlight a UK EOSC activity on our EOSC Association national page, please contact paul.richards@ukri.org and helen.clare@jisc.ac.uk

The [UK EOSC mailing list](#) is available to share information and continue discussions.